

DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES IN STEP OF INITIAL EDUCATION OF HANDBALL PLAYERS

Pavlov Shoislom Kalibayevich¹

Uzbekistan state university of physical education and sport,
Chirchik, Uzbekistan,

Yusupova Zamira Esonbekovna²

Uzbekistan state university of physical education and sport,
Chirchik, Uzbekistan,

Isroilov Rustam Iskandarovich³

Uzbekistan state university of physical education and sport,
Chirchik, Uzbekistan.

<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejar-v03-i02-p1-26>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th January 2023

Accepted: 07th February 2023

Online: 08th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Training of young athletes, the system of prestigious competitions, achieving high goals from the system of training athletes, technical and tactical directions of Islamic exercises by sport.

ABSTRACT

This article presents an orderly ratio of loads aimed at developing general physical fitness of young handball players. From this, the effectiveness of the distribution of training loads was confirmed according to all indicators, in which there was a reliable improvement in the handball players of the experimental group on the tests evaluating the general physical fitness.

Now the younger generation is given in a healthy atmosphere special attention. Our president "Future happiness of our country and offering a great service to the highest happiness in the path of the future work" said our olympic championship explain quite high the flag of Uzbekistan at prestigious competition in handling the training of young athletes want to change the system completely.

President said the development of a batter system of training young athletes and punctuality, as well as, in foreign countries, including Korea, Japan, European countries use a system of training athletes in order to reach higher where the foundation.

Great young athletes for injuries not occurred since the first round of training in a sport physical exercises on the technical, tactical trained according to the foundation in order to achieve great results. Handball in the process of development of the physical attributes of their age, sex and anatomical, physiological indicators of workload, they organisms qualified trainer experience

The aim of research work:

Distribute to workload initial education among 10-12 year old and teach the scientific literature for development physical qualities of children. That on base to develop and control handball players.

The tasks of research work:

We research to achieve this goal we have set for the following tasks.

- ✓ To study a thematic of the scientific literature and scientific articles.
- ✓ Study and analyze workload used to exercises
- ✓ Evaluating and controlling 10-12 year old children with physical tests

The object of my scientific work have carried out during the period from September to December in 2021. Our experience have carried out № 2 children's and youth's handball school in Tashkent city Yakkasaray district. Then we divided up two groups that experimental and control groups. Our experimental group took part 10 junior handball players.

The control group children's physical evaluation before research

№	First name. Second name.	Running 30 meters distance (minute)	From the standing long jumb	Throwing long distance of the handball's ball(meter)		Running 100 meters race pendulum (minute)
				Right hand	Left hand	
1	A-v F	6,8	150	10	5	32,3
2	A-v G	7,1	140	12	7	31,5
3	B-v R	7,3	155	10	5	33,5
4	D-v T	6,3	160	11	6	30,1
5	G-v D	6,1	135	13	8	34,2
6	J-v A	6,7	165	12	7	29,8
7	K-v R	6,5	150	15	5	31,7
8	R-v L	6,1	145	14	9	30,6
9	H-v J	6,9	130	14	7	30,3
10	X-v A	6,2	160	10	6	30,1
	X	6,6	149	12,1	6,5	31,4

The Experimental group children's physical evaluation before of research

№	First name. Second name.	Running 30 meters distance (minute)	From the standing long jumb	Throwing long distance of the handball's ball(meter)		Running 100 meters race pendulum (minute)
				Right hand	Left hand	
1	D-v J	6,9	155	10	5	33,3
2	H-v A	6,5	146	11	7	32,1
3	F-v K	6,8	154	10	6	31,6
4	L-v Q	7,5	148	12	5	31,1
5	R-v D	7,2	160	14	4	30,5
6	K-v E	7,6	163	14	5	31,7
7	J-v H	6,2	150	9	6	30,8
8	Q-v L	6,3	140	11	7	29,9
9	S-v B	7,2	145	12	5	29,5
10	P-v G	7,4	155	10	4	32,4
	X	6,9	151,6	11,3	5,4	31,2

10 players have applied to have the test in the table above 5 lines is shown. We didn't expect. So we recommend to use our exercises. During 4 months we had testing in order to determine the effectiveness our experimental groups. The results at the end of research are as follows:

The control group children's physical evaluation before research

№	First name. Second name.	Running 30 meters distance (minute)	From the standing long jump	Throwing long distance of the handball's ball(meter)		Running 100 meters race pendulum (minute)
				Right hand	Left hand	
1	A-v F	6,1	155	11	6	31,1
2	A-v G	6,8	145	13	6	31,5
3	B-v R	6,7	150	11	5	32,6
4	D-v T	6,1	165	10	5	29,8
5	G-v D	5,7	140	12	7	32,6
6	J-v A	6,1	160	13	6	29,2
7	K-v R	6,1	155	14	6	31,2
8	R-v L	5,9	150	15	7	29,5
9	H-v J	6,2	140	16	6	29,6
10	X-v A	5,8	165	12	5	29,3
	X	6,1	152,5	12,7	5,9	30,6

The Experimental group children's physical evaluation before of research

№	First name. Second name.	Running 30 meters distance (minute)	From the standing long jump	Throwing long distance of the handball's ball(meter)		Running 100 meters race pendulum (minute)
				Right hand	Left hand	
1	D-v J	6,2	160	12	7	30,3
2	H-v A	5,9	155	13	9	30,6
3	F-v K	6,1	170	14	7	29,2
4	L-v Q	6,5	165	15	8	28,9
5	R-v D	6,2	170	16	6	28,8
6	K-v E	6,8	164	15	8	29,3
7	J-v H	5,6	162	12	7	29,3
8	Q-v L	5,8	168	13	9	29,1
9	S-v B	6,3	152	15	6	28,8
10	P-v G	6,1	165	16	5	30,2
	X	6,1	163,1	14,1	7,2	29,4

As a result of research of the experimental and control group that less than the control group the traditional quality and efficiency of the program stand.

Rather this term is used regularly in the experimental group exercises, the development of the standard and the quality effective of physical exercises.

References:

1. Абдалимов А.О., Абдалимов О.Х., Физическая подготовка гандболистов высшей квалификации, Т.Н.Қори-Ниёзий номидаги Ўзбекистон Педагогика фанлари илмий-тадқиқот институтининг илмий-услубий мақолалар тўплами №3, 2020. 65-68 б.
2. Абдалимов А.О., Исроилов Р.И., Ёш гандболчиларнинг чидамлилигини назорат қилиш услублари., «Современная наука в олимпийском спорте», халқаро илмий-амалий онлайн конференция. 2020. 173-175 б.
3. Ш.К. Павлов. “Спорт педагогик маҳоратини ошириш” (Гандбол) ўқув қўлланма – Т: “Илмий-техника ахбороти-пресс нашриёти”, 2021. 208 б.
4. А.Ш. Мўминов. “Спорт педагогик маҳоратини ошириш” (Гандбол) ўқув қўлланма – Тошкент: “Илмий-техника ахбороти-пресс нашриёти”, 2021. 200 б.
5. Р.И. Исроилов. Тайёрлов даврида ёш гандболчиларнинг тезкор-чидамкорлигини ривожлантириш восита ва усулларининг самарадорлигини тадқиқ этиш. Фан-спортга илмий-назарий журнал №3, 2021., 15-17 б.
6. Взаимосвязь показателей технических действий и скоростно-силовых способностей на этапе углубленной подготовки молодых дзюдоистов, А Акбаров, Теория и методика физической культуры 64 (2), 50-56, 2021
7. Павлов Ш.К, Акрамов Ж, Абдурахмонов Ф “Гандбол” Дарслик 2005й.
8. Исроилов Р.И.1, Хабибжонова Х.М.1 «Контроль физической и технической подготовки студентов общего курса занимающихся гандболом» Инновационные технологии в спорте и физическом воспитании подрастающего поколения, сборник статей по материалам X научно-практической конференции с международным, Страницы: 86-88. Москва-2020.